
ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE OF FOOD, BEVERAGES AND TOBACCO MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This work studied the effect of organizational climate on employee performance of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to; examine the effect of team commitment on job satisfaction of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria and determine the effect of reward recognition on productivity of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study adopted a survey design. The population of the study was six thousand three hundred (6,300). The sample size of 400 was adopted using Freund and William's statistic formula. The study used stratified random sampling procedure and structured questionnaire was used to select respondents. Simple regression statistical tool was employed to test two formulated hypotheses. The findings revealed that team commitment had a significant positive effect on job satisfaction of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria ($F=338.378$, $pv .000<0.05$) and reward recognition had a significant positive effect on productivity of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria ($F=231.361$, $pv .000<0.05$). The study thus recommends that management of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State to ensure that they checkmate team commitment provided by employees whether it satisfied job expectations. This includes ensuring that every team have a leader and sub leaders who will always supervise and monitor their activities and character wise every day.

Keywords: Organizational Climate, Employee Performance, Team Commitment, Job Satisfaction, Reward Recognition

INTRODUCTION

Today's organizations are operating in a very dynamic and highly competitive environment. To remain significant in the market, organizations have to attract and retain suitable people as well as supporting them to improve their performance (Mira, Mohamed & Nevien, 2021; Anitha, 2020). Organizational climate is the common opinion of employees who work and play vital roles in the organization. It is the individual insights regarding the organizational techniques, policies and practices (Subina, 2019). It signifies the psychological environment of the organization comprising of individual opinions outlined upon micro events that happen to them as well as to others around, over a period of time. It is the set of considerable things in the work

environment, observed straightforwardly or incidentally by the members over their work and satisfaction (Subina, 2019).

Historically, the construct of climate preceded the construct of organizational culture. The social context of the work environment, termed “atmosphere,” was discussed as early as 1910 (Hollingworth & Poffenberger, 1917), and was among one of the many topics investigated at the National Institute of Industrial Psychology (NIIP) during the 1930s in Britain (Kwaitkowski, Duncan, & Shimmin, 2006). Climate was formally introduced in the 1960s, primarily based on the concepts proposed by Kurt Lewin (Lewin, 1951; Lewin, Lippitt, & White, 1939) and followed by empirical research (Litwin & Stringer; 1968; Stern, 1970). Organizations were examined from a cultural perspective as early as the 1930s (Trice & Beyer, 1993). The concept and framework of organizational climate has evolved over a long period of time with the earliest available reference on the concept/framework of organizational climate being traced to 1939 (Lewin, Lippitt & White), which was then referred as „Social Climate”, as stated by Srivastav (2009).

Organizational climate is the form of the existing conditions and nature of organizational life observed by the employees (Taştan & Güçel, 2019). Organizational climate as supportive environment is believed to enable behaviour among the workforce to flourish (Noor, *et al.*, 2021). The Organizational Climate enables the firm to recognize the insufficiencies in connection with different organizational aspects, such as organizational structure, organizational recognition, organizational identification, employee compensation system, interaction level, physical atmosphere, organizational culture, etc. It is the evident attribute of a firm and its sub-systems as simulated in the manner in which an organization deals with its acquaintances, team members and organizational difficulties. It is comparatively continuing excellence of the in-house atmosphere that is practiced by its employees which influences their functioning and can be described in terms of the values of a particular set of activities in the firm (Subina, 2019).

Existing studies have provided results on the correlation between organizational climate and employee performance. For example, the study of Maqbool, *et.al* (2020) states that all variables measured namely role, clarity, respect, communication, reward system, career development, planning, decision making, innovation, relationships, teamwork, support, conflict management, commitment, morale, training, and learning and the direction of the company are correlated to the job satisfaction. In terms of organizational climate and employees’ organizational commitment, Berberoglu (2018) presented a positive correlation between the two variables. Similarly, organizational climate correlates with work engagement. Organizational climates such as clarity, standards, individual responsibility, flexibility, reward, recognition, identification, structure, and team commitment affect the work engagement of the employees (Abun, *et.al.* 2021, Chaudhary, *et.al*, 2023, Clement & Eketu, 2019). It is also true with individual work performance as pointed out in the study of Permarupan, *et.al* (2023). A positive work environment affects the employees’ work behavior positively, reversely, it can influence counterproductive behavior (Lipińska-Grobely, 2021, Batubara and El-Hami, 2018).

An employee who has a high level of performance generally has a high level of engagement with his work (Syafuddin, 2022). Where the employee tries his best to achieve work targets that have been set at work, besides that he is also an employee who feels his work is an important thing to maintain and fight for (Gibbons, 2015). Companies that have employees with high levels of work engagement will help and encourage

companies to further develop and get full support from all employees for every policy implemented (Huynh, 2019). Furthermore, prior work engagement affects employee performance through employee creativity, organizational culture, organizational climate, leadership style, and employee empowerment (Iqbal, 2019). It is at this juncture, that the study investigates effect of organizational climate on employee performance of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Climate within the workplace is increasingly recognized as a fundamental aspect of organizational effectiveness and competitiveness in today's globalised world. Organizational climate has become a strategic approach aimed at enhancing the efficiency of organizations. This approach involves the deliberate actions taken by organizations to foster greater inclusion of employees from diverse backgrounds within the organizational framework.

The strategic nature of managing a climate workforce becomes evident when considering the pursuit of long-term objectives and corporate goals. Numerous successful large corporations have effectively overseen diverse teams to achieve their firm aims. Outside this, it has led some organizations into poor working environment, low working conditions, lack of compensation management, inadequate incentive schemes, unforeseen promotion opportunities, high job security, poor equipment compensation, low provision of accommodations/supports etc.

It is well established that employees who derive job satisfaction and productivity from their jobs are more likely to develop positive organizational climate, thus suggesting that manufacturing firms can indeed exert an influence on employee performance. Thus, it becomes apparent that there are areas within empirical research that remain unexplored, particularly in the realm of organizational climate and employee performance within food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms situated in Enugu State. The researcher bridged this gap by undertaking this study.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the effect of organizational climate on employee performance of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. Other specific objectives were to;

- i. Examine the effect of team commitment on job satisfaction of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the effect of reward recognition on productivity of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will add to the existing body of knowledge on organizational climate and employee performance by bringing them to front the need for the integration of workers climate and its significance, if any, to economic growth of Nigeria. Their inclusion in decision making and capacity building will be important in empowering the organizations and its workers. In the peripheral areas of the state, organizational climate equips them with necessary team commitment, reward recognition and competencies coupled with creativity; it can spur employment and development of organizations. Secondly, on the academic and research front, this study will be invaluable in filling the gaps in practice by examining how organizational climate and employees

changes narrative towards mind set of individuals that they cannot fit in policies. In the long run this organizations would be used as a model for the development of different societies but in a context specific way. In policy cycle, the study findings will be invaluable to the government establishment in planning and implementation of climate project in the organization.

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study examined the effect of organizational climate on employee performance of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study concentrated on staff of two selected food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria, namely Coca Cola and Nigeria breweries Plc. The study also covered dependent and independent variables, the independent variable is organizational climate decomposed by team commitment and reward recognition while the dependent variable remains employee performance proxied by job satisfaction and productivity.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Organizational Climate

Organizational climate has a great influence on people performance through its impact on individual motivation and job satisfaction. Organizational climate is a set of individual, organizational and environmental nature and features which gives characteristics to the organization by sorting out from others, perceived by people and has an effect on their behaviors (Berberoglu, 2018; Taştan & Güçel, 2019). Concerning organizational climate, Maqbool, *et.al.* (2020) defined it as “a source of pleasant conditions at the workplace; it is a positive emotional state which can be measured from positive job experiences (Maqbool, *et.al.*, 2020).

Elements of Organizational Climate

Organizational climate has been defined as an internal environment of an organization that characterizes an organization resulting from the behavior and policies of an organization (Ahuja & Naula (2016). For example, Drigo Consulting Group (2023) identifies flexibility, responsibility, standards, rewards, clarity, and team commitment. While Davidson, *et.al* (2021) pointed out leader facilitation and support; professional and organizational esprit; conflict and ambiguity; regulations, organization, and pressure; job variety, challenge, and autonomy; job standards, workgroup cooperation, friendliness, and warmth. Balachandran and Thomas (2017) also named several dimensions of organizational climate namely welfare concern, norms and standards, interpersonal relations, recruitment and training, recognition and encouragement, job security, fair rewards, job autonomy, freedom and control, and red tape. Lone, *et.al* (2017), however, classified only two dimensions of organizational climate which are called human relation climate and rational goal climate.

Team Commitment

Forsyth, (2020) defined a team as "structured groups of people working based on well-defined common goals that require coordinated interactions to perform certain tasks". For the team to accomplish the goal, one must have the knowledge, skills, and specialized ability to contribute (Levi, 2001). As Preda (2021) stated, team members must have complementary skills that they use to carry out their tasks to accomplish the goal. The philosophy behind teamwork is that the intelligence of a group exceeds the intelligence of a person considering the right conditions are met (Luden, (2019).

Reward/Recognition

These two terms are often used interchangeably, and people use them to mean the same thing. In the business, the reward is defined as "the return for the performance of the desired behavior and positive reinforcement" (Aksakal & Dağdeviren, 2022). It is a strategy to motivate and reinforce good behavior. Thus, when the word reward and recognition are used together, a tangible reward for excellent performance and recognition in the form of acknowledgment or praise must be given to the individual who performs well. Correspondingly, Abun, *et.al* (2021) highlighted that employees must be rewarded monetarily or advancement, or non-monetary reward in form of recognition or praise.

Employee Performance

Patro (2019) defines employee performance as "the accomplishment of the assigned task for achieving the organizational goal". Orta (2018) likewise defines employee performance as "how well an employee is executing the expected related work activities". These two definitions were published in IGI Global and used as the main concept in the conduct of performance appraisal of Pereira (2020). They refer to employee performance in terms of outcome, productivity, and quality. Sinha (2021) stated that employees' performance is depending on the willingness and also the openness of the employees itself on doing their job. He also stated that by having this willingness and openness of the employees in doing their job, it could increase the employees' productivity or job satisfaction which also leads to the performance.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction can be defined as a sense of employee achievements and success-es. It is generally believed that it is directly related to productivity and work performance, as well as to personal well-being. Job satisfaction means doing the work one likes, doing it well and being rewarded for own efforts (Aziri, 2021). Job satisfaction is considered as one of the main factors of the effectiveness and efficiency of business organizations. In fact, the new managerial paradigm, which insists that employees should be treated primarily as someone who has their own needs and personal desires, is a very good indicator of the importance of job satisfaction in modern enterprises.

Productivity

Productivity is a commonly used but often poorly defined term that regularly appears in both academic and practical discussions. Definitions of productivity seem to be dependent on the reviewer's point of view and the context in which it is used. Studies on technology, engineering and economics, three broad industry categories, all examine productivity from slightly different viewpoints (Ghoabadian & Husband, 2019). Bernolak (2017) productivity means "how much and how good we produce from the resources used," whereas The European Association of National Productivity Centres (EANPC, 2022) defines productivity as "how efficiently and effectively products and services are being produced." Efficiency in this context can be seen as "doing things right" or utilizing resources to accomplish desired results (Grünberg, 2021).

Organizational Climate Effect on Employee Performance

Sambandam and Chockalingam (2019) proved that there is significant relationship between dimensions of organizational climate and employee performance. Hirlak *et al.* (2018) proved that dimensions of organizational climate affect employee performances. Githinji (2017) proved that there is a positive relation between organization climate and employee performance, since organizational climate for career advancement and job

satisfaction should employ practices such as job security and quality of work by ensuring availability of work tools, safe and healthy work environments.

Theoretical Framework

Ethical Climate Theory (ECT)

Ethical climate theory was developed by Kohlberg's in 1969. According to research on moral growth might be seen as a pivotal moment in the evolution of ECT because of its firm grounding in ethical philosophy. According to Kohlberg, there are three pillars of ethics: egoism, utilitarianism, and deontology. The term "egoism" refers to actions motivated only by one's own self-interest. Utilitarianism refers to an approach that prioritises the welfare of the greatest number of people or groups. Deontological behaviour entails adhering to guidelines set out by society for the greater benefit. To identify and classify the many sorts of ethical climate that might evolve in a company, Victor and Cullen utilized a sociological-theoretical approach to organizations (Gouldner, 1957).

ECT bases its moral judgments on the triad of egoism, altruism (or utilitarianism), and principle (or deontology). According to the available evidence, one of the three ECT notions will arise within a sample and come to describe the field's general ethical environment. The ECT proposed by Victor and Cullen expands on this idea by detailing the many forms of ethical action and decision-making that might alter the prevailing ethical norms. Individual, organizational, and societal (i.e., the community or society in which the organization operates) levels of analysis were found to be significant in the study by Victor and Cullen in order to comprehend ethical climate. By comparing egoism, altruism, and principle to each of these criteria, Victor and Cullen developed a theoretical model of the current ethical environment. The empirical tests conducted by Victor and Cullen revealed five distinct conceptualizations of ethical environment, including a caring climate, an instrumental climate, an independent climate, a rules and law and code climate, and a law and code climate. Those that study ethical climate maintain its validity and identify five distinct ethical climates (Agarwal & Malloy, 1999; Kehoe & Wright, 2013; Schminke *et al.*, 2005).

Empirical Review

Team Commitment and Job Satisfaction

Maduagwuna, Anah and Ohanyere (2023) examined employees' commitment and organizational performance in onitsha north & south local government area, Anambra State. The study examined employees' commitment and organizational Performance State in Onitsha North & South Local Government area. Anambra State. The findings of the study revealed, affective commitment has significant positive influence on the quality of service in Onitsha North & South Local Government Council.

Obiakor, Anah, Udodiugwu and Obiakor (2024) examined job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behaviour of academic staff in federal polytechnic, Oko, Anambra State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to examine the relationships between employees' skill variety and employees' altruism, and employees' commitment and employees' conscientiousness. The study was anchored on Job Characteristics Theory. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. From the test of hypotheses, the first finding of the study revealed that skill variety had a significant positive relationship with employees' altruism (t-value of 66.715 and p-value = 0.000 at 0.05 level of significance and low positive value of $r = 0.338$), and the second test

revealed that employee commitment had a significant positive relationship with employees' conscientiousness (t-value of 65.591 and p-value of 0.000 at 0.05 level of significance and a moderate positive correlation value of $r = 0.638$) of the polytechnic.

Reward/Recognition and Productivity

Sikira, Madaba and Filbert (2024) studied impact of recognition on employees' performance in the manufacturing industries in Tanzania in Kanya. This study examined the impact of recognition on employees' performance in the manufacturing industries in Tanzania by using a case of Tanga Cement Company. The study found that media representation boosts employees' desire to perform better, highlighting the importance of visibility and validation.

Organizational Climate and Employee Performance

The results Mutonyi *et al.* (2020) also stated that the organizational climate plays an important role in creating good performance and increasing employee creativity. Organizational climate shows a positive and significant relationship with two creative performance variables, namely innovative individual and creative individual.

This is in line with previous research conducted by Obeng *et al.* (2021). The results of the research prove that organizational climate positively and significantly affects employee performance, they say that when role clarity, participatory decision making, rewards, communication, are practiced in the organization, it is expected that employees will show behaviors that lead to improved performance, not only by achieving the work they do but also by adapting to changes in the work environment.

Mira, Mohamed and Nevien (2023) examined the effect of organizational climate on employee performance mediating by intrapreneurial behaviours in Nigeria. The findings of this research reveal that organizational climate has a positive influence on employee performance. As well, the organizational climate has a positive influence on intrapreneurial behaviours. And the direct effect between intrapreneurial behaviours and employee performance is statistically significant.

Aulia, and Ribhan (2023) conducted a study on effect of job stress and organizational climate on turnover intention with job satisfaction as a mediation variable in Nigeria. The results of the study show that job stress has a positive and significant impact on the turnover of employees in the housing development company in Bandar Lampung, while organizational climate has a negative and significant impact on employee turnover. The results of the study show that job stress has a positive and significant impact on the turnover of employees in the housing development company in Bandar Lampung, while organizational climate has a negative and significant impact on employee turnover.

Latifah and Reni (2023) studied effect of organizational climate on team performance: the role of knowledge sharing as mediator in Nigeria. The study aims to analyze the impact knowledge sharing as mediator on the relationship between organizational climate and team performance. The results of analysis revealed that organizational climate positively and significantly affected knowledge sharing and team performance. Next, knowledge sharing also explained team performance positively. Interestingly, the study found that knowledge sharing mediated the relationship between organizational climate and team performance.

Royyan and Susanto (2023) examined the effect of organizational climate on employee performance universitas in Nigeria. The purpose of this study was to examine and analyze the mediating role of organizational commitment and job satisfaction in the influence of organizational climate on employee performance. This study used a cross sectional method with 58 respondents. The results showed that organizational commitment does not mediate the effect of organizational climate on employee performance and job satisfaction mediates the effect of organizational climate on employee performance.

Ureltsetseg, Amarsanaa, Temujin and Erdembileg (2024) examined the impact of organizational climate, development, work result on clinical governance in India. The aim of this study is to analyze the influence of organizational climate, development, work result on clinical governance. In our study of many others, we analyzed three hypotheses, and two of them had a positive relationship and one of them had a negative relationship with considered impacts. The result of data was determined online between August 2022 and February of fiscal 2023.

Gap in Empirical Review

Most recent literature on the organizational climate have recognized the tremendous effect on employee performance which has been recorded in recent times. But this scenario revealed that organizational climate indicators have not been extensively and empirically investigated by other researchers. Therefore, a study on the organizational climate and employee performance of food, beverage and tobacco context was crucial in order to approve or disapprove the varying viewpoints on this study area which would lead to the expansion of the body of knowledge in this study area. This was the gap the study filled.

METHODOLOGY

For this study, a causal research design was utilized to investigate how a specific independent variable (Organizational Climate) affects the dependent variable (Employee Performance) in Nigeria. This research design is based on the assumption that a cause-and effect relationship exists between the two variables. Primary data were collected from selected food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms using questionnaire as instrument for data collection. The target population for this study included junior and senior staff of Coca Cola and Nigeria Breweries Plc. The staff formed the target population of this study. Thus, the total population of the study was 6,300 selected banks are as shown in table 3.1 below.

Table 1 Description of Population

Firms	Staff	Total
Coca Cola	4,800	4,800
Nigeria Breweries.	1,500	1,500
Total	6,300	6,300

Source: Banks Internal Reports, 2025

The total population of the study was six thousand three hundred (6,300). the sample size was 400, using Freund and William's statistic formula as quoted by (Uzoagulu 2009). A stratified random sampling procedure was used for selecting the participants in this study. This technique was employed to ensure a fairly equal representation of the variables for the study. The stratification was based on selected two firms from 17 food,

beverages and tobacco sectoral group quoted in Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN). Within each section, the selection of staff was done by simple random sampling.

Bowley's (1976) proportional allocation formula was used.

$$nh = \frac{n(Nh)}{N}$$

Where:

Nh = Group population from each stratum

n = overall sample size

N = the overall population

nh = sample size from each stratum, in this case each firm.

Table 2: Proportionate Allocation of Questionnaire to Firms

Thus:

S/N	Names of Firms	Total Population	Proportionate Allocation
1	Coca Cola	4,800	$\frac{4,800}{6,300} \times \frac{400}{1} = 305$
2	Nigeria Brewery	1,500	$\frac{1,500}{6,300} \times \frac{400}{1} = 95$
	Total	6,300	400

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The study used structured questionnaire as a tool for data collection. The questionnaires were distributed during data collection to ensure an extensive examination and understanding of the phenomenon as well as youths involvement in community development and its effect in the diverse communities in the study area. The data collection process involved various response categories including; respective registered youth groups in Nkanu General Assemble.

The instrument was given to five experts from the industry and academia to measure face and content validity. To make sure that the research instruments applied in the work are valid, the research ensured that the instrument measure the concept they are supposed to measure. Validity is the extent to which differences in scores on measuring instrument reflect true difference among individuals on characteristics that are being measured rather than constant random errors. A proper structuring of the questionnaire and a conduct of a pre-test of every question contained in the questionnaire was carried out to ensure that they are valid.

Reliability analysis is the measure of the study research instruments consistency in reflection of overall reliability of the study variables (Nyukuri, 2020). The scores obtained from the reliability analysis are correlated with other scores from other items in the instrument (Ronoh, 2018). The study will measure the internal consistency and determine the correlation of items using the Cronbach alpha coefficient which is the most commonly used measure of research instrument reliability with the most acceptable alpha being 0.7 and above out of 1.0 (Cohen and Sayang, 2010).

Mugenda and Mugenda (2019), data analysis includes sorting, editing, coding, cleaning and processing of data. The study used primary data from the different respondents that were reached and responded to the questionnaires. The data was analyzed both qualitatively and quantitatively. The data was analyzed qualitatively by sorting and categorizing data that was obtained from the structured questionnaires according to thematic areas. Precisely the responses from different respondents were compared to determine the most occurring responses from different respondents were compared to determine the most occurring responses and these were used in the analysis and interpretation of the data. Quantitatively, the statistical package for social scientists (SPSS v 24) was employed to draw simple regression tool as a way of testing formulated hypotheses.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

Data Presentation

Table 3: Percentage of the Questionnaire Issued and Returned

Questionnaire	Number of Respondents	% of Respondents
Returned	320	80
Not Returned	80	20
Total	400	100

Source: Field of Survey, 2025

From table 4.1 above, it shows that 320 copies of the questionnaire were duly completed and returned representing 80 percent, while 80 copies of the questionnaire were not duly completed and returned from the respondents representing 20 percent. Therefore, the total of 320 copies was used for analysis representing 20%.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Team commitment has no significant positive effect on job satisfaction of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

H₀₁: Team commitment has significant positive effect on job satisfaction of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R-Square	Adjusted Square	R-	Std Error of the Estimate
1	.591	.318	.312		.562
a. Predictors: (Constant), Team commitment					

The F-statistic (338.378) shows that team commitment has significant positive effect on job satisfaction. The (R²) of 31% indicates that any 1 percent increase in funds will result in 31% variation on job satisfaction and that could be explained by other factors in the model. This implies that there was a strong significant positive effect of team commitment on job satisfaction of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Table 5: ANOVA

ANOVA					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1 Regression	55.378	1	65.378	338.378	.000 ^b
Residual	31.663	319	.316		
Total	117.041	320			

a. *Dependent Variable: job satisfaction b. Predictors: (Constant), team commitment.*

The result of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for regression coefficient revealed ($F=338.378$, p value = 0.000a). The results indicate that the P value is 0.00 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, this implies that the regression model statistically and significantly predicts the outcome variable and is, therefore, a good fit for the data. This is an indication that team commitment has a strong significant positive effect on job satisfaction of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Reward recognition has no significant positive effect on productivity of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: Reward recognition has no significant positive effect on productivity of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Table 6: Model Summary

Model	R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std Error of the Estimate
1	.392	.312	.321	.339

b. Predictors: (Constant), Reward recognition

The F-statistic (331.361) shows significant positive effect of reward recognition on productivity. The (R^2) of 31% indicates that any 1 percent increase in on reward recognition will result in 31% variation on productivity and this could be explained by other factors in the model. This implies that there was a strong significant positive effect of reward recognition on productivity of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Table 7: ANOVA

ANOVA					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1 Regression	59.378	1	55.278	231.361	.000 ^b
Residual	35.663	319	.311		
Total	115.041	320			

b. *Dependent Variable: productivity, b. Predictors: (Constant), reward recognition*

The result of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for regression coefficient revealed ($F=231.361$, p value = 0.000a). The results indicated that the significance of the P value is 0.00 which is less than 0.05, Therefore, this implies that the regression model statistically and significantly predicts the outcome variable and is, therefore, a good fit for the data. This is an indication that there was a strong significant positive effect of reward recognition on productivity of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Objective One: Examine the effect of team commitment on job satisfaction of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. With view in hypothesis one, it shows that team commitment has a strong significant positive effect on job satisfaction of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in

Enugu State, Nigeria. In related study of Maduagwuna, Anah and Ohanyere (2023) examined employees' commitment and organizational performance in onitsha north & south local government area, Anambra State. The findings of the study revealed, affective commitment has significant positive influence on the quality of service in Onitsha North & South Local Government Council.

Objective Two: Determine the effect of reward recognition on productivity of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. In aforementioned view with evidence of hypothesis two result proves that there was a strong significant positive effect of reward recognition on productivity of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. In similar way the study is in agreement with Sikira, Madaba and Filbert (2024) who studied impact of recognition on employees' performance in the manufacturing industries in tanzania in Kanya. The study found that media representation boosts employees' desire to perform better, highlighting the importance of visibility and validation.

Summary of Findings

- i. Team commitment had a significant positive effect on job satisfaction of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria ($F=338.378$, $pv .000<0.05$).
- ii. Reward recognition had a significant positive effect on productivity of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria ($F=231.361$, $pv .000<0.05$).

Conclusion

In the light of findings, the researcher concludes that organizational climate had significant positive effect on employee job performance. Therefore, study also concluded that team commitment and reward recognition had significant positive effect to job satisfaction and productivity of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

With evidence of findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made;

- i. The study thus recommends management of food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State to ensure that they checkmate team commitment provided by employees whether it satisfied job expectation. This includes ensuring that every team have a leader and sub leaders who will always supervise and monitor their activities every day.
- ii. The management should also provide reward recognition support at all times especially in times of need. This is a form of motivation for one another and will help employees discharge their duties to maximum level in order to increase productivity output.

REFERENCES

- Abun, D., Menor, R.I., Catbagan, N.C. Magallanes, T. & Ranay, F.B. (2021). Organizational climate and work engagement of employees of divine word colleges in Ilocos Region, Philippines. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 10(1), 107-121.
- Agarwal, J., & Malloy, D. C. (2019). Ethical work climate dimensions in a not-for-profit organization: An empirical study. *Journal of business ethics*, 20(1), 1-14

- Ahuja, J. & Narula, V. (2016). A demographic study on organizational climate: indian vs. multinational it companies. *Pacific Business Review*, 8(8), 1-12
- Aksakal, E. & Dağdeviren, M. (2022). Analyzing Reward Management Framework with Multi- Criteria Decision-making Methods. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 147(1), 147-152.
- Anitha, J. (2020). *Determinants of employee engagement and their impact on employee performance. International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 63(2), 308 - 323.
- Aulia, S.V and Ribhan, N.M (2023). The effect of job stress and organizational climate on turnover intention with job satisfaction as a mediation variable, *International Journal of Social Science and Education*, 2(12), 56-78
- Aziri, B (2021). Job satisfaction: a literature review, *Management Research and Practice*, 3(4), 77-86.
- Balachandran, M. & Thomas, I. (2018). Dimensions of organizational climate. *The Psychespace*, 1(1), 27-36
- Batubara, M. & El Hami, A. (2018). Does organizational climate effect on employee happiness among lecturers in indonesia? *10th International Conference on Language, Humanities, Education and Social Sciences*, 18(1), 67-89
- Bernolak, I. (2017). Effective measurement and successful elements of company productivity: The basis of competitiveness and world prosperity, *International Journal of Production Economics*, 52(1-2), 203-210
- Chaudhary, R., Rangnekar, S. & Barua, M.K. (2023). Organizational climate, climate strength, and work engagement. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 133(1), 291 – 303
- Clement, O.I. & Eketu, C.A. (2019). Organizational climate and employee engagement in banks in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research Sciences, Technology, and Technology*, 5(3), 11-23
- Cohen, J. M. (2010). 'Capacity building in the public sector: A Focused Framework for Analysis and Action' in *International Review of Administrative Sciences*; 61,407-422. Sage (London, Thousand Oaks, New Delhi).
- Creswell, C. & Purcell, K. (2014). Youth participation and the environmental community projects: do we know what works? *Environmental Science and Technology*, 33 (16), 2685–2692
- Cullen, J. B., Parboteeah, K. P., & Victor, B. (2003). The effects of ethical climates on organizational commitment: A two-study analysis. *Journal of business ethics*, 46(2), 127- 141.

- Davidson, M., Manning, M., Timo, N., & Ryder, P. (2021). The dimensions of organizational climate in four- and five-star Australian hotels. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 25(4), 444– 461
- Drigo Consulting Group (2023). *Creating a performance enhancing organizational climate*. Retrieved from <https://www.drigoconsultinggroup.com>
- EANPC, J.A. (2022). The effect of training and development on employees' performance. *Presented At Safaricom Limited Call Centre*, 2(3), 1-49
- Forsyth, D.R. (2020). *Group dynamics, 5th edition*. Wadsworth: Cengage Learning, Belmont
- Ghoabadian, A. & Husband, T (2019). Measuring total productivity using production functions, *International Journal of Production Research* 28(8),1435-46.
- Gibbons, P. (2015). *The science of successful organizational change*.
- Githinji, Naomi Wanjiku (2017). Influence of organizational climate on employee performance in state corporations in Kenya. A case of Kenya Industrial Estates Limited. *Strategic Journal of Business and Change Management*, 2(3), 11-24
- Gouldner, A. W. (1957). Cosmopolitans and locals: toward an analysis of latent social roles. *International Administrative Science Quarterly*, 2(4),281-306.
- Gurhan, G., Gunduz, U., Kemal, K., & Lutfihak, A. (2021). Effects of innovation types on firm performance, *The Scientific and Technological Research*, 5(22), 1-22.
- Hirlak, Bengü, Çiftçi, Gamze and Balıkçı, Orhan. (2018). *The effects of organizational climate on the employee performance: the mediating role of employees' creativity*. Researchgate. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330088816>.
- Huynh, S. (2019). Substantial interest of business intelligence: An implementation approach for used in practice. *Test Engineering and Management*, 81(1091), 1091–1095.
- Iqbal, H. N. I. A. (2019). Employee engagement and job performance in Lebanon: the mediating role of creativity. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 68(3), 506–523.
- Kehoe, R. R., & Wright, P. M. (2013). The impact of high-performance human resource practices on employees' attitudes and behaviors. *Journal of management*, 39(2), 366-391

- Latifah, H. S and Reni, Y (2023). The effect of organizational climate on team performance: the role of knowledge sharing as mediator, *International Journal of Management Studies and Social Science Research*, 5(5), 2-21
- Lipińska-Grobelny, A. (2021). Organizational climate and counterproductive work behaviors the moderating role of gender. *Int J Occup Med Environ Health*, 34(4), 513-525.
- Lone, J.A., Garnås, A., Myklebust, T., Bjørklund, R., Hoff, T., & Bjørkli, C. (2017). Organizational climate and investigation performance in the Norwegian police: A qualitative study. *Journal of Investigative Psychology and Offender Profiling*, 14(3), 227-245.
- Luden, D. (2019). *Are two heads better than one? psychology today*. Retrieved from <https://www.psychologytoday.com>
- Maduagwuna, I.A, Anah, A.N and Ohanyere, C.P (2023). Employees' commitment and organizational performance in onitsha north & south local government area, Anambra State, *Academia Networks International Journal of Management Studies*, 8(4), 203-220
- Maqbool, S., Ismail, S.A.M.M. & Maqbool, S. (2020). Organizational climate and job satisfaction in 21st century higher educational institutes. *Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews*, 8(4), 577-586.
- Martin, K. D., & Cullen, J. B. (2006). Continuities and extensions of ethical climate theory: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of business ethics*, 69(2), 175-194
- Mira, H.K, Mohamed, H.W & Nevien, F.K (2023). The effect of organizational climate on employee performance mediating by intrapreneurial behaviours, *International Journal of Management*, 2(2), 1-23
- Mutonyi, B. R., Slåtten, T., & Lien, G. (2020). Organizational climate and creative performance in the public sector. *European Business Review*, 32(4), 615–631.
- Noor, Hazlina Ahmad, Aizzat, Mohd Nasurdin and Siti, Rohaida Mohamed Zainal (2021). The role of organisational internal ecosystem in fostering intrapreneurship spirit. *World Review of Business Research*, 1(5), 38-51
- Nyukuri, D. W. (2020). Influence of project management practices on project sustainability: a survey of trans nzoia county government, Kenya. *International Journal of Recent Research in Commerce Economics and Management*, 7(1), 230-254

- Obeng, A. F., Zhu, Y., Azinga, S. A., & Quansah, P. E. (2021). Organizational climate and job performance: Investigating the mediating role of harmonious work passion and the moderating role of leader-member exchange and coaching. *SAGE Open*, 11(2), 1-21
- Obiakor U.J., Anah S.A., Udodiugwu M.I & Obiakor J.N. (2024), Job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behaviour of academic staff in federal polytechnic, Oko, Anambra State, Nigeria. *British Journal of Management and Marketing Studies* 7(1), 1-18.
- Orta, I.M. (2018). *Exploring emotional intelligence at work: a review of current evidence*. Hershey, Pennsylvania: IGI Global Publisher of Timely Knowledge
- Patro, C.S. (2019). *Performance appraisal*. Pennsylvania: IGI Global: Publisher of Timely Knowledge.
- Pereira, J.L. (2020). *Approaches and methods for individual performance assessment in information systems projects. in handbook of research on the role of human factors in it project management*. Hershey, Pennsylvania: IGI Global Publisher of Timely Knowledge
- Permarupan, P.Y., Saufi, R.A., Kasimc, S.R. & Balakrishnan, B.K. (2023). The impact of organizational climate on employee's work passion and organizational commitment. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 107(1), 88 – 95.
- Preda, M. (2021). *Comportment organizational*. Romania: Polirom
- Royyan, F.R & Susanto, T (2023). The effect of organizational climate on employee performance universitas, *International Journal of Economics, Business and Management Research*, 7(5), 23-56
- Sambandam, R & Chockalingam, M (2019). *Influence of organizational climate on employee performance in manufacturing industry*. *Suraj Punj Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 9(1), 146-178
- Schminke, M., Ambrose, M. L., & Neubaum, D. O. (2005). The effect of leader moral development on ethical climate and employee attitudes. *Organizational behavior and human decision processes*, 97(2), 135-151.
- Sikira R., Madaba R and Filbert R (2024). Impact of recognition on employees` performance in the manufacturing industries in tanzania: a case of tanga cement company, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 2(3), 1-20.
- Sinha, Y. & Lei, X. (2021). Exploring the impact of leadership characteristics on subordinates' counterproductive work behavior: *From the Organizational Cultural Psychology Perspective*. *Frontier in Psychology*, 13(1), 8-18

Syaifuddin, F. R. A. Y. L. N. (2022). Can life satisfaction become an important role in increasing employee performance? a case study. *Journal of System and Management Sciences*, 12(6), 379–397.

Taştan, S.B & Güçel, C (2014). *Explaining intrapreneurial behaviors of employees with perceived organizational climate and testing the mediating role of organizational identification. A Research Study among Employees of Turkish Innovative Firms*. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 150(1), 862 – 871

Ureltsetseg B., Amarsanaa B., Temujin A and Erdembileg T (2024). *The impact of organizational climate, development, work result on clinical governance: the Case of Mongolia*. *J Huma Soci Scie*, 7(1), 01-09.